

Tree Mourners: Ecosomatic Performative Actions for a Dying Forest

(Performance-Lecture Script — Raffaele Rufo, GAIA Conference, Madrid 2025)

Total duration: 30 min

Spoken time: ~20 min

Audiovisual / Somatic / Silence: ~10 min

[00:00 – 02:00 | PROLOGUE]

(The projection begins with a still image of the cut trunk of a pine tree in the middle of the street in the city of Ostia, on the periphery of Rome.)

RAFFAELE (softly, with pauses):

Forests are dying...all over Europe...not only in the Amazon...this is an exemplary case of the many ecological crises we are facing as a species.

Yet most of us seem indifferent or unable to see that death, let alone to process that death. We live in the city after all, and cities have swallowed that forest that once was the ideal place to build a city. (Pause)

Today we have lost that capacity to grieve and mourn — both human and nonhuman loss — and the two are deeply connected.

In Southern Italy, the land of my ancestors, people once mourned the dead in public. These laments, rooted in the Greek heritage of Magna Graecia, embraced death as part of life. Nature was integral to these cultures, a stable reference and source of the sacred. Without it, human grief and mortality could not be understood.

Ecosomatics is a counter-cultural force that calls us to grieve **with** the Earth — **to transform** loss into practices of attention, care, and renewal.

(long pause, breath)

Because in mourning, we can discover new forms of life and relationality.

(pause)

[02:00 – 05:00 | INTRODUCTION]

Buenos días... *good morning everyone.*

Thank you for joining this performance lecture at GAIA —

“Acciones performativas ecosomáticas de duelo por un bosque moribundo” - Tree Mourners.

My name is **Raffaele Rufo**,

I am an **ecosomatic artist-scholar based in Rome and affiliated to Tampere University in Finland**. I work across performance, pedagogy, and philosophy.

My research explores **ecological grief** as an embodied practice of participation — where perception itself becomes reciprocal, and where art can help us remember how to listen to the ecological crises and how to cultivate individual and collective responsiveness.

(pause)

Before I continue, I'd like to share a short *glosario*, a small glossary of words we'll encounter today — to start attuning our bodies to their resonances:

- **Grief — el dolor**, the raw affect of loss, the inner trembling.
- **Mourning — el duelo**, the process of giving form and time to that loss, so that healing can occur.
- **Lament — el lamento o la lamentación**, the embodied expression of mourning — through voice, gesture, or ritual — that allows sorrow to move through the body and transform.
- **Ecosomatics — la ecosomática**, the study and practice of how the human body, as an ecology of sensory systems, participates in the living intelligence of the Earth.
- **Embodied participation — la participación encarnada**, the act of engaging the world not only through ideas, but through touch, breath, and movement.

(pause, warm tone)

These are the key coordinates of what I call **ecosomatic mourning** — a way of grieving with, rather than for, the world.

(beat)

I met Valérie de la Dehesa in September this year, when she presented her work at *Genius Loci*, the international symposium of ecosomatic arts I curated in Rome — a gathering on *bodies, places, and communities*.

It's a joy to continue that dialogue here, where GAIA focuses on **Sculpture, Body, and Territory**.

(pause)

Today, I'll share fragments - sound, video and words - of my ongoing ecosomatic research — culminating in the performative actions of **Tree Mourners**, created on the coast of Rome in January 2025, after years of working among the dying pine forests of Ostia.

[06:00 – 10:00 | WHAT IS ECOSOMATICS?]

(Projection: subtle moving image — close-ups of breathing tree bark, wind, the sea.)

Ecosomatics is an emerging somatic, educational, artistic research practice and in the particular case of my own research an evolving **arts-led methodological and pedagogical paradigm** — It is a field where movement, creation, pedagogical, philosophical, and ecological sensibilities converge.

In ecosomatics, we don't simply *represent* nature;
We explore **the reciprocity of perception** in practice.
We study how perception changes when the body listens *with* the land.
As Thomas Hanna wrote in 1970's and 1980's,
"Somatics is the field in which the human body is experienced from within."
Ecosomatics extends this to the more-than-human:
the forest, the soil, the water — all sensing back.

(gentle emphasis)

When we really listen to what is happening around us, we start seeing death. We start feeling grief. (long pause)

Ecosomatics asks:

How do we mourn a dying world **through** our bodies?

How can embodied participation help societies move from anaesthesia to care?

(beat)

In my research I speak of **embodied participation** as a lever for ecological transformation — a way of bridging ecological data with lived experience and artistic creation.

In Italy, that inquiry took root in the Roman coast —

A milestone in this process was *La Selva*, a residency where in October 2023 we welcomed a group of 40 artists, educators and scholars from all over the world...and worked among burnt and regenerating forests.

As co-facilitator I felt the responsibility of putting participants in the condition of witnessing the aftermath of the great fire of 2000 which burnt 300 hectares of forests

... and also the insect invasion that killed more than 50 000 pines.

From there, the work evolved into **Tree Mourners**,
a performative action for the trees that never recovered.

(I have written several articles and chapters on ecosomatics so if you are interested to know more about this growing field, you can check my research gate profile or personal website)

[10:00 – 15:00 | SOMATIC EXPLORATION #1 — Embodied Memory of Mourning]

(The audience is invited to settle. Raffaele speaks slowly, guiding.)

Before we enter the performative actions of Tree Mourners,,
I'd like to invite you into a brief **somatic exploration**.

(pause)

Please find a comfortable position — sitting —
allowing your spine to lengthen,
your breath to flow.

(slow rhythm)

Feel the weight of your body being poured into the chair through your sitting bones,
the ground beneath your feet.

Let your breath expand and contract,
like the tide of the sea.

Play with folding your pelvis inward and outward as the body is rolling on the sitting bones.

Now — close your eyes.

(pause)

Imagine a moment in your life when you encountered **death** —
perhaps a relative, a friend, an animal,
a tree cut down,
a landscape that disappeared.
Don't force an image — allow the body to remember.

(Pause)

As you breathe,
notice how memory has texture, temperature, rhythm.
Notice where grief lives in your body.

(pause)

Now I will read a memory of mine —
from the death of my uncle, in the South of Italy.

I invite you to sense how the body holds memory of grief,
and how it releases them.

(reads, calm, resonant)

The day after my uncle Genesisio died, a large group of relatives, friends and acquaintances gathered around his bed, in his home, for the last VISIT before the funeral procession and the burial. Many of them I had not seen in many years. Time felt curvilinear, as if past and future could not be separated. When I entered the room his dead body was shining in the open coffin with a powerful presence. There were people crying, touching the body and kissing him, whispering, praying, comforting each other, or simply witnessing in silence. My cousin had put a sprig of asparagus in his hands. My uncle was keen on collecting asparagus and offering them to friends and family as delicious ingredients. The asparagus and his skin were so beautifully attuned in texture and density that I felt as if an old kinship between humans and plants was being revealed.

(long silence, then softly)

Take a breath in.

Exhale through your mouth.

(pause)

Slowly open your eyes.

Gracias... *thank you.*

[15:00 – 19:00 | FROM LA SELVA TO TREE MOURNERS]

(Projection: drone aerial of Castel Fusano forest — burnt and regenerating pines, followed by the group singing “La Selva” prefica song. No speech for 30 seconds, then voice resumes over images.)

La Selva residency in Rome was a collective encounter with a place of **fire and regeneration**, a forest scarred by catastrophe.

Working there, we practised **embodied participation** —

walking, sensing, touching the charred trunks,

learning from the slow regeneration of the forest.

We discovered that ecological grief is not an abstract feeling;

it is a bodily process,

a rehearsal for reconnection.

We played a VISIT to the dead trees (**“il visito” is the name of the old ritual for the deads I have just tried to evoke**).

Video 1 — “La Selva / The Forest Seen from Above” (1 min silent)

(Drone view of forest, then bottom view of group singing.)

(Silence. Then softly:)

When we see the forest from above,

we see the wound.

When we sing from below,

we enter that wound.

(fade to black)

(pause)

(gentle emphasis)

But after *La Selva*, I realised that I needed to encounter the grief for the tens of thousands of sea pines killed by an insect carried to Italy in the containers shipped from North America.

In Ostia, where I currently live, the urban forest has been sick for years, and thousands of trees are dead while still standing on their roots — with their grey crowns. Thousands of them have been felled in the last couple of years. Just after La Selva residency ended the city of Rome began the felling and explantation of all the dead pine trees lined up on the beautiful avenue connecting the campsite where participants resided while in Rome and the sea.

Video 2 — “The Pine Avenue”

(iPhone footage of the avenue of felled trees.)

These are the trees along the road to the sea —
once guardians of the avenue,
now ghosts in daylight.
In these absences,
the work of mourning begins.

(pause)

After the residency I also felt the urge to honour the death of the abandoned pine stumps in the streets and urban forests of Ostia,
where death and neglect coexist with daily life.

Why had they been left dying? Why wait for so long before recognising their illness and taking care of them? It was an insect carried into containers from North America that killed them. So the mainstream story goes...Other stories talk about private interest to build inside the natural reserve ... to empty it of trees so that economic development could finally happen...

And I have been there day after day, to witness the political economy of a dying forest. Just to find out that a contract of 60 million euros has been signed by the local authority with the company that will “take care” of felling and explanting the dead trees..

It is there, at the intersection between the forest and the city, the ecological and the cultural that my ecosomatic work began to merge with my **cultural roots** —
the mourning rituals of Southern Italy,
and the laments of ancient Greece.

(pause)

This encounter between **embodied participation** and **ancestral mourning traditions** opened the path to *Tree Mourners*.

The practice of *lamentación* — the sung, somatic expression of loss — became both method and language.

(gentle emphasis)

In ecosomatic terms, lament is a **gateway** into mourning.

It transforms grief from isolation into resonance.

As Guy Cools reminds us, in his book on “performing lament”

“Lament exteriorises loss to make it relational.”

And as my fieldwork confirmed,

to lament the death of trees is to recognise our own entanglement in their dying.

(pause)

¿Cómo se llora un bosque?

How do we mourn a forest?

That question — personal, ancestral, ecological —

led to the creation of **Tree Mourners: ecosomatic performative actions for a dying forest.**

[19:00 – 25:00 | TREE MOURNERS — THE ECOSOMATIC PERFORMATIVE PRACTICE]

(Projection shifts to “Tree Mourners” film excerpts, numbered 1–6, integrated with live narration.)

Before we enter the visual material,

*I want to share briefly **how Tree Mourners was made** — its **methods**, its **somatic and choreographic language**.*

*This work arises from a lineage of **ecosomatic practices** —*

methods that use the lived body as a site of perception and knowledge.

We worked with a small ensemble of four performers —

Helen Spackman, Valentina Vitolo, Chiara Marchesano, and Tommaso Collalti —

*developing movement and voice practices that link **somatic listening** with **ritual gesture**.*

Our process combined:

- **Eco-somatic prompts** — invitations to feel one's own body through the felt sense of another being, a tree, the wind, or the soil.
- **Tactile–kinesthetic processes** — mirroring, attunement, and contagion, allowing one body's vibration to move through another.
- **Choreographic structures** inspired by ancient mourning rituals — balancing the solemn control of codified gestures with the freedom of ecstatic improvisation.
- **And movement patterns of passage** — falling, debarking, waking, burying, washing — each a phase in a collective journey from separation to transformation.

What you are about to see are fragments from that process —
 Performative actions filmed between the dying forests of Ostia and the sea.
 Sometimes the visuals will stay behind me as I speak.
 Other times, they will take the foreground —
 letting the work itself speak.

(beat)

Let us begin.

Video 3 — “The Wake”

(At sunset, four performers with a candle.)

In many traditions worldwide
 The wake is the waiting with the dead
 Throughout the night
 To be with the dead
 to allow the soul to leave the body.
 I feel a sense of imprisonment for these dead trees
 Left standing in the urban forest of Ostia.
 As if they needed the support and care
 To make the journey out.

(whisper)

The forest is dying,
 and yet in our lament we breathe for it.

Video 4 — “Debarking”

(Performers removing bark from fallen tree; silence.)

(After 15 seconds)

To debark is to make death visible.

It is to remove the simulacrum of life

and reveal the raw, moist, unfinished matter beneath.

The bark becomes skin —

and through the touch,

the body assumes responsibility.

(pause)

In ecosomatic terms,

*this is the **aesthetics of abandonment** —*

And an ethics of tenderness which meets the desperation for our inability to respond collectively to ecological destruction.

Video 5 — “Burial / Re-barking”

(Human body partly covered with bark; dim light.)

Here, the bark returns to cover the human body.

We exchange skins —

bark for flesh,

flesh for bark.

Life passes into matter,

and matter into life.

(slow)

We try to cross from representation.

to interpenetration.

Grief for human loss intersects grief for ecological loss.

Video 6 — “Ablution / The Sea”

(Women mourning together at the sea; gentle water sound.)

At the sea, in the sharing of grief,
Through repeated gestures and lamentations
grief liquefies.

We wash the body of the forest
in the salt of the Earth’s tears.
Water regenerates —
and so, the lament dissolves into care.

(silence as video fades)

(softly)

In this work, the ensemble performs **mourning as participation** —
not as spectacle, but as performative practice.

We are not illustrating death.
We are processing it *with* the forest.

Our gestures draw on ancient traditions —
the *prefiche* of Southern Italy,
the laments of Magna Graecia,
echoes of Dionysian rites,
Greek tragedy before philosophy.
As Guy Cools writes,
mourning is not a mental or moral act;
it is a **somatic experience of transformation**.

(pause)

When we mourn together — humans, trees, soil, sea —
we cultivate shared responsibility.
We learn again that **to live is to be entangled**.

(short silence)

*These methods turn mourning into a **participatory ecology**.
The performance is not a representation of loss —
it is a practice of interdependence.*

As the philosopher David Abram reminds us,
“Reciprocity is the very structure of perception.”
Through ecosomatic practice,
we experience that reciprocity as movement, breath, and care.

[25:00 – 29:00 | SOMATIC EXPLORATION #2 — “Lament for a Dying Forest” (field recording, 4 min)]

(Sound of the 4-minute field recording begins — solo lament recorded during the performative actions in Ostia. While it plays, he speaks gently.)

As you listen,
I invite you to find your own **posture of grief**.
Let your body shape itself —
perhaps seated, perhaps standing.
Let breath connect with the lament.

(pause)

Touch the part of the body where you sense grief

Feel the resonance of the mourning voice through your ribs,
your hands,
your spine.

(midway through recording)

Now — allow a **gesture of care** to emerge.
A simple movement —
for yourself,
for the forest,
for someone or something you love.

(music continues, then fades into silence)

Stay with the echo of the sound in your body.

(pause)

Gracias... *thank you*.

[29:00 – 30:00 | CLOSING REFLECTIONS]

*Ecosomatic mourning is not about sadness alone.
It is about **re-membering** —
literally, putting the body back together with the Earth.*

*In Tree Mourners, we face a paradox.
To give voice to the forest, we inevitably use the human body,
the human voice, the human lens.*

¿Es esto antropocentrismo?

*Perhaps — but an **anthropocentrism inhabited consciously**,
one that bends toward humility instead of mastery.*

*As Robin Wall Kimmerer reminds us,
“People once knew that other beings are persons too —
each with gifts, responsibilities, and intentions.
This is not a mistaken anthropomorphism,
but a recognition of kinship.”*

(pause)

*To speak through our bodies is not to dominate;
it is to **risk transformation**.
Natasha Myers suggests that what we call anthropomorphism
may in fact be our capacity to be moved by other modes of embodiment,
to let vegetal and elemental rhythms inflect our own.*

(slow)

*So, rather than escaping the human,
we pass through it —
opening our sensorial thresholds to the more-than-human chorus.
The body becomes a **membrane of reciprocity**,
where grief and regeneration meet.*

*From Kimmerer’s teachings to the polyphonic laments of the South of Italy,
from Baka forest songs in Central Africa to Andean rituals of reciprocity,
many traditions remind us:
life is sustained by giving back what we receive.
In ecosomatic practice, this reciprocity becomes tangible —
each breath, each gesture, each lament
a small act of returning.*

(gentle emphasis)

If anthropocentrism isolates, reciprocity reunites.

If grief contracts, mourning expands.

*Through this work we learn that the human is not the measure of the world —
but a temporary vessel through which the world becomes audible.*

(soft breath)

So let us listen,

not above the forest,

*but **within its breathing.***

(looks toward the screen)

To mourn a tree is to recognise our shared fragility,

our entanglement,

and our responsibility.

(pause)

I want to end by quoting the words of the lament we have listened to just a few minutes ago:

Let it die, Let it die...

I cannot do that. I just can't.

I feel like dying. I can't do that now.

But you can't stop the ocean. Let it die.

(Silence. The image fades to black. End.)

Thank you.